

A Case Report

Rehabilitation of Anterior Malposed Implant With Customized Abutment

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Abstract

Improper placement of dental implants is an undesirable complication in implant-based prosthetics. Many cases that require restorative correction, often known as "rescue cases," involve either new issues or attempts to fix irreversible implant situations. One effective way to address these prosthetic challenges is by using cementable solutions. This problem arises from misaligned implants, which dentists find difficult to correct due to the lack of angle-adjustable abutments provided by manufacturers. The recommended treatments in these scenarios are either Implant Innovations' universal castable long abutment (UCLA) (Palm Beach Gardens, Florida, United States) or a customized abutment made from titanium alloy impression coping for the Core-Vent implant (Paragon, Calabasas, California, United States). The Department of Prosthodontics received a referral for a patient with a misaligned anterior implant that needed rehabilitation. This case report describes the treatment strategy used to address a buccally positioned implant.

Introduction

The primary reason patients seek improved cosmetic and functional dental solutions in clinics is to replace missing teeth. Prosthetics offer a way to restore missing teeth, boosting patient satisfaction by enabling efficient chewing while also maintaining dental health and structural integrity^[1]. Dental implant restorations have become a dependable choice in dentistry, providing a consistent treatment approach. However, implant misplacement can occur, leading to prosthetic complications. Despite considerable progress, implant-supported restorations are still prone to issues. These complications can arise from inadequate treatment planning, poor case selection, lack of proper communication among the patient, surgeon, prosthodontist, and lab technicians, or subpar operator techniques, among other factors. Misplaced dental implants during

surgery are a frequent clinical problem. Addressing prosthetic needs in cases with misaligned or improperly positioned implants poses a challenge for both prosthodontists and lab personnel. A variety of solutions, including angulated abutments, castable abutments, and, in extreme cases, removable prostheses, have been developed to tackle these issues^[2]. Ongoing research in dental implantology has resulted in the expanded use of dental implants across various clinical settings. However, as dental implants become more common, so do the complications, particularly when implants are not placed correctly. Restoring implants that are in challenging positions is a major challenge for restorative dentists, lab

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technicians, and patients, especially when dealing with the critical maxillary smile zone. Addressing such cases may require prosthetic adjustments, surgical corrections, or a combination of both.^(3,5) The purpose of this clinical report is to highlight that the success of an implant involves more than just achieving osseointegration; it also depends on correct placement and the creation of a prosthesis that seamlessly blends with the surrounding teeth. However, complications can occur when implants are misaligned or when there's limited interarch space for future prostheses, especially in the aesthetic zone. These complex scenarios require a customized treatment plan to meet the patient's aesthetic expectations while ensuring the implant is successfully restored with a fixed prosthesis.^(6,7) In this situation, standard prefabricated abutments aren't sufficient. Custom-designed abutments are required to improve the emergence profile and ensure the prosthesis conforms to the arch shape. The choice of abutments is crucial for the success of a fixed prosthesis. Custom abutments can be used for cement- or screw-retained single crowns or bridges. Abutments can

influence the transmission of forces to the surrounding bone by adjusting the stress and strain distribution on the implant. When constructing implant-supported prostheses, parallel abutments are commonly used. However, additional surgical procedures might be needed to position an implant correctly in three-dimensional space^[8-10]. This case report discusses the prosthetic management of misaligned implants in the anterior aesthetic zone.

Case Report

A 24 years-old male patient was referred by the Department of Oral Surgery. Two years ago, he was symptom-free, but then he had a road traffic accident that caused him to lose his permanent right central incisor. Since he wanted a fixed dental solution, the plan was to place an implant in the position where his right and left lateral incisor had been. Since due to insufficient amount of bone the implants were placed malaligned. (Fig-1) The patient's primary concern was aesthetics so 13 and 23 was prepared to improve the esthetic of the patient.

Figure- 1

The patient had no notable medical history. A thorough assessment and evaluation were carried out using diagnostic models and existing radiographs. Despite the implant's suboptimal placement, it was decided to load the implant with a customized abutment, following the patient's wishes and after obtaining informed consent. Rehabilitating the implant with standard abutments was challenging. To prevent gingival impingement from conventional abutments, a customized abutment was chosen as the best option. Thus, it was determined that using a customized abutment to rehabilitate the implant would be the most

suitable course of action. An impression coping was secured to a implant, and an open tray impression was taken using putty and light-body polyvinyl siloxane material. A cast was then created after attaching a laboratory analog. Jig trail was done and the final open tray impression was made taken using putty and light-body polyvinyl siloxane material. (Figure-2)

A gingival or aesthetic mask was applied to the impression in the 12, 11, 21, 22 region to simulate soft tissue on the cast. The fabrication process for the custom abutments involved creating a wax pattern, which was then cast in metal.(Figure-3)

Figure- 2

Figure- 3

An intraoral metal try-in was performed for the cast abutment, and the marginal gingiva level was marked. (Figure-4)

The shade was selected using the Vita classic shade guide (Vita, Yorba Linda, California, United States). A porcelain-fused-to-metal crown was fabricated for the cast abutment, with pink porcelain applied to the gingival

area. Before cementing the crown, all excursive contacts were identified and removed. The abutment was tightly screwed into position, and then the crown was cemented onto it.(Figure-5)

The screw access hole was filled with composite and final delivery of the prosthesis was done. Patient was advised to maintain her oral hygiene. (Figure-6)

Figure- 4

Figure- 5

Figure- 6

Discussion

The position of the implant plays a crucial role in ensuring both the aesthetics and functionality of the prosthesis. Thorough treatment planning and accurate diagnosis are essential for successful implant placement. Prosthodontists often face aesthetic and functional challenges when placing implants in the anterior region. Gingival ceramics can adjust the emergence profile of an implant inserted from the apical coronal position. ⁽¹¹⁾ Implant placement is influenced by several factors, including surgical stents, radiographic assessments, soft and hard tissue anatomy, abutment selection, the design of the final prosthesis, and the patient's overall health. ⁽¹²⁾ In this situation, the implant was positioned too far toward the buccal side relative to the surrounding teeth. Two options were given to the patient: remove the

misaligned implant and either fit a fixed prosthesis or insert a new implant in the correct position, or attach a permanent prosthesis to the existing implant to gradually shape the surrounding gingiva. The patient chose not to remove the misaligned implant. When dealing with misaligned implants, prefabricated or custom-angled abutments can be utilized to restore function, comfort, and aesthetics. ^(13,14) Aesthetic issues in dental implant procedures are frequently caused by incorrect prosthesis shade selection and a lack of interdental papillae. Therefore, to ensure a successful outcome in dental implant rehabilitation, the implant-supported prosthesis must meet the aesthetic requirements of both the dentist and the patient. Key factors to consider include using larger crowns, incorporating artificial gingiva, utilizing angled abutments, applying custom porcelain coatings,

and, when needed, performing secondary grafts.⁽¹⁵⁾ Misalignment of a maxillary anterior implant makes it difficult to maintain and reproduce the natural mucogingival architecture around it.^(16,17) Ideally, the implant body should be perpendicular to the curves of Wilson and Spee, as these curves result from compressive stresses along the implant's longitudinal axis. Maintaining axial parallelism reduces the overall stress on the implant system and helps prevent related biological and mechanical issues, such as abutment fractures and screw loosening. However, anatomical variations, like bone concavities on the maxillary facial side or the lingual surface of the jaw, might require the clinician to place the implant at an angle. In implant dentistry, implant placement at angles exceeding 25° and the use of custom abutments can carry risks. Despite advances in computer-aided design and manufacturing, casting remains a commonly accepted method for producing these abutments. Cast abutments can be a practical choice when inter-occlusal space is limited, the implant is outside the arch, or the implant angle is more than 30°. Furthermore, cast abutments are often more affordable.^(18,19) Cast abutments are divided into two types: cast-to and castable. The key benefit of cast-to abutments is the precise fit of the connection. On the other hand, castable abutments have a connecting region that's cast, which might result in less accuracy.⁽²⁰⁾

Limitation

Numerous studies on the impact of abutment rotational flexibility on implants have found that abutment movement can cause screw loosening. (21) A significant limitation in the case described above is the incorrect angulation and placement of the implant. This raises concerns about long-term success, as the joint between the angled abutment and the implant could create unfavorable forces, potentially leading to implant failure. According to Binon, increasing the rotational flexibility of the screw from 2° to 3° reduced the number of cycles under cyclic loads before screw loosening by 26% (22). Screw loosening usually occurs due to mismatched components, inadequate tightening, excessive stress on the system, or poorly designed screws. Other contributing factors include bending stress on the screw, the settling effect, and reduced preload [23]. In this situation, the implant's poor positioning greatly undermines its long-term viability. Nonetheless, steps have been taken to extend the implant's lifespan by removing excursive contacts.

Conclusion

Custom castable abutments are considered an option, not a definitive solution, for managing implant-supported prostheses in these scenarios. Accurate diagnosis and treatment planning are crucial for the successful restoration of implants. When the implant is positioned outside the arch, rehabilitation becomes challenging and requires special care. Customized abutments are often the best treatment approach in these cases. The need for clinical precision is highlighted by the buccally placed access hole, which may require pink or gingival porcelain to conceal the site and meet aesthetic standards. This detailed approach underscores the importance of aesthetics in achieving patient satisfaction. In the case described, misaligned implants can be corrected with prosthetic rehabilitation using customized castable angled abutments.

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